

b

X = protein lost
● = motif/domain lost

	MadBub						Knl1			Cdc20	Mad1	CycA	CycB	
Conserved features:	KEN1	TPR	Dbox	ABBA1	KEN2	ABBA2	GLEBS	CDI	kinase	MELT	MIM	D-box/KEN	presence of the SAC	
Interacting with:	Cdc20						Bub3	Mad1	-	Bub3	Mad2	Cdc20		
<i>Homo sapiens</i>	2	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	STOP	
<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i>	2	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	STOP	
<i>Dictyostelium discoideum</i>	1	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	STOP	
<i>Bigeloviella natans</i>	2	●	●	incomplete sequence	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	STOP	
<i>Aurantiochytrium limacinium</i>	1	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	STOP	
<i>Arabidopsis thaliana</i>	3	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	STOP	
<i>Naegleria gruberi</i>	2	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	STOP	
<i>Trypanosoma brucei</i>	0	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		
<i>Monocercomonoides exilis</i>	1	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	x	x	●	●	
<i>Trichomonas vaginalis</i>	2	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	x	x	●	●	
<i>Carpediemonas membranifera</i>	1	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	x	?	?	?	STOP
<i>Carpediemonas frisia</i>	1	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	x	●	●	●	STOP
<i>Kipferlia bialata</i>	1	●	●	●	●	●	incomplete sequence	●	●	x	incomplete sequence	●	●	STOP
<i>Spironucleus salmonicida</i>	1	incomplete sequence	●	●	x	x	●	●						
<i>Trepomonas sp. PC1</i>	1	incomplete sequence	●	●	x	x	●	●						
<i>Giardia intestinalis</i>	1	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	x	x	x	●	
<i>Giardia muris</i>	1	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	x	x	x	●	

other Eukaryota

Metamonada

c

	KEN1	Dbox-like	ABBA1	KEN2	ABBA2	GLEBS	CDI
<i>H. sapiens</i>	EWELSKENVQPLRQGRIR	QRSTLAELEKSK	RITVFDE	PRAKENELQ	SFTPYVEE	GFESFEEIRAEVF	PSPTVHTKEALGFIMNMF
<i>S. cerevisiae</i>	EIEETQKENVLPKKEGRS	-----	KNNVFVD	ERNKENLNR	KLPFRDS	EEFNTEEILAMIK	PTVTAFSKDAINEVFSMF
<i>D. discoideum</i>	DWENTKENIVPLKTRGRD	TRSALEGTISS	GFQIFDD	NKHKENTQL	GFQIYCDQ	HEISFEEYRASLF	PTMTIHTKQAFHDMAMF
<i>A. thaliana</i>	EWELFKENVRPLKGRNR	PSRSFGTLLSR	PFAIYAD	ERNKENNSL	TFEYFVDE	-----	VDPTINMKEAMNTINMF
<i>B. natans</i>	EIEGSKENIQPLKRRNR	-----	-----	-----	-----	RETSFEEYRAMIY	PSPTIHTKQAFHDMAMF
<i>A. limacinium</i>	DWEQCKENAMPKRRGRD	SRRSLQPIRSR	RFEVFEQ	ELQKENSID	AFDVYVEE	-----	EDMTINTRLALDDMFEMF
<i>N. gruberi</i>	EFEAAKENIIPKGGRR	QRLPFNSLAKK	NEVIYDE	EQEKENEK	HFSIFVDE	AEFTFEELRAMHY	-----
<i>Monocercomonoides sp.</i>	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	ARRSVEEEREMTN	no motifs
<i>T. vaginalis</i>	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	TSRSFVEARLADM	<i>S. salmonicida</i>
<i>C. membranifera</i>	AWEEKKENVLPRAAQR	VRAALMDLDAQ	-----	DTVKENFGR	DFEVFI DD	-----	<i>Trepomonas sp.</i>
<i>C. frisia</i>	-----	-----	-----	DVTKENIGR	DFDILVDD	-----	-----
<i>K. bialata</i>	EAARDKENLQPLDGGRR	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----
<i>G. intestinalis</i>	-----	-----	-----	KAKRENSKA	-----	SDVSFEEQRLLDI	-----
<i>G. muris</i>	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	SFISPEEQHLLDL	-----

	MIM (Mad1)	MIM (Cdc20)	Dbox/KEN (Cyclin A)	Dbox (Cyclin B)	phosphosite repeats (MELT)
<i>H. sapiens</i>	RTKVLHMSLNPT	EAKILRLSGKPO	PQRTVLGLLTAN	RPRTALGDI GNK	MDPT
<i>S. cerevisiae</i>	KIRILQLRDGP	NKRILQYMPPEP	VQRLALNNVTNT	VPRTILGNVTNN	MDPT
<i>D. discoideum</i>	KTQVLFHNSNPS	ESKILSFKSKAP	HKRVALYDVT HQ	SHRGALSDLTNN	MDPT
<i>A. thaliana</i>	NTRVLRMNT	HTRILAFRNKQP	KKRVLVGLGELPNL	QNRKVLGDI GNL	MDPT
<i>B. natans</i>	TKVLLHMRFN PQ	ESRVLAFKFKAP	-----	TSRRALGDI SNA	MDPT
<i>A. limacinium</i>	TKVLLHMTFNPE	SSKILAYRQKAP	-----	-----	MDPT
<i>N. gruberi</i>	KFKILLHMKLNPE	DAKILALTEKAP	-----	-----	MDPT
<i>Monocercomonoides sp.</i>	-----	-----	QSRREILRDVINS	TQRTCLGDI SNQ	MDPT
<i>T. vaginalis</i>	-----	-----	RRRALSSTVAGT	RRRKALEQITNT	MDPT
<i>C. membranifera</i>	SYIVMHMSLNPT	TSSIVVHAKSAAP	HQRVALSRVSNIT	EHKAPLGDIVS	MDPT
<i>C. frisia</i>	PKVLLHATHNPI	EQKVIHSRSEAP	DKKENIRKLOEA	-----	MDPT
<i>K. bialata</i>	APKVLALSGKAP	-----	-----	LTRAPLRDVGRT	MDPT

H. sapiens (21) *D. discoideum* (5) *S. cerevisiae* (6) *B. natans* (8) *N. gruberi* (1) *A. thaliana* (5) *A. limacinium* (11)